

Use of Social Media in Promoting Breast Cancer Awareness among Malaysian Women of Generation Y: A Conceptual Framework

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 05, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: February 02, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Breast Cancer Social media Perceived Interactivity Review Intensity Source Credibility</p> <hr/> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4495161</p>	<p><i>With the distinctive features of social media, researchers have argued that these emerging tools might be useful in respect of exchanging health-related information through an interactive and collaborative mechanism. For example, social media provides a persuasive, accessible, and broader reach of information for promoting breast cancer awareness among the public. Through a theoretical review of the existing research, this paper develops a conceptual framework to examine the influence of social media interactivity and source credibility on users' attitude to and awareness of breast cancer among Malaysian women, specifically, Generation Y. The framework also examines the moderating effect of review intensity on attitude towards using social media and breast cancer awareness. The proposed conceptual framework includes essential users' concerns to enhance the use of social media to increase breast cancer awareness. The paper highlights the proposed relationships for further empirical studies to explore and demonstrate the usefulness of the conceptual framework.</i></p>

Introduction

Breast cancer is the most occurrence of cancer among women around the world and the second common cancer overall. Recent data indicate that breast cancer is responsible for an estimated 627,000 deaths in 2018, which is approximately 15 % of all cancer deaths among women (WHO, 2018). Malaysia has the worst survival rates for breast cancer compares to other Asia Pacific countries. The majority of breast cancer patients diagnosed at a quite late stage (Mastura & Azlina, 2018), which makes breast cancer a leading cause of death especially among young Malaysian women. This is due to several reasons such as poor awareness, the absence of screening programmes, and cultural restrictions and limitations. Moreover, the 2018 Globocan reported that most of the diagnosed incident are at ten years or younger than their Western counterparts (Bray et al., 2018). Thus, there is an urgent need to find a key mechanism of promoting Malaysians women awareness, particularly young women.

One way to promote Malaysian women awareness is the utilizing of technology such as social media that enable users to disseminate and exchange health-related information effortlessly, and seamlessly, such a mechanism would immensely promote breast cancer awareness. The proliferation of the internet and the two-way interactions have changed the role of users from recipients into a generator for different types of content, which is a new reality in the healthcare setting (Johnston, Worrell, Di Gangi, & Wasko, 2013; Lapointe, Ramaprasad, & Vedel, 2014). The advent of social media contributes to the real life in different aspects such as organization performance (Tajudeen, Jaafar, & Ainin, 2018), marketing and purchase behaviours (Alalwan, 2018; Sheth, 2018) tourists, and political campaigns (Dimitrova & Matthes, 2018; Hausmann et al., 2018). Social media usage was also expanded to social marketing, specifically healthcare context. Clinicians or patients are increasingly engaging and participating in health information through these online platforms (Benetoli, Chen, & Aslani, 2018; Carley et al., 2018).

Thus, it is critical for healthcare practitioners, and policymakers to understand women attitude toward using social media to exchange health-related information about diseases detection, prevention, and treatment. Malaysia has one of the lowest survival rates of breast cancer in the Asia Pacific region due to the late

detection of this disease, around 50% of incidents seek treatment at a relatively late stage which makes it harder to treat (Indramalar, 2018). The poor awareness of breast cancer is further reflected in higher toll and expenditure on public health services. Besides, the anxiety disorders among caregivers' Malaysian families who have breast cancer patients, especially those who are receiving oncologic treatment (Din et al., 2017).

Even though, social media such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and YouTube have enabled its users to exchange health information with others, what is facilitate user's engagement in such online environment still a remaining question (Tha'er & Bohari, 2016; Z. Yan, Wang, Chen, & Zhang, 2016). For instance, online users might have a strict concern in terms of revealing, and sharing information or personal experiences about breast cancer which restrain users engagement (Bansal & Gefen, 2010), which might return to the users perception on social media interactivity as a critical determinant of engagement in health-related information exchange through online platforms.

Another concern determines users' attitudes toward online health-related information exchange is the source credibility of the information, or content (De Meulenaer, De Pelsmacker, & Dens, 2018; Filieri, Hofacker, & Alguezaui, 2018). Source credibility refers to the judgment by information receivers in which they consider that the communicators are knowledgeable and trustworthy sources (Nan, 2013; Yoo & Gretzel, 2011). This indicates that perceived interactivity and source credibility are vital determinants of attitude toward social media use for health-related information exchange.

Also, this paper extends prior research by examining the moderating effect of reviews intensity. Social media provides an attractive environment for users to seek, share, support and recommend each other's with different contexts, compliance to an individual behavior such as health-related information exchange is also restricted the intensity of these actions. Prior research, demonstrated that the high intensity of online reviews such as liking number, rating, quantity, and accuracy play an essential role to adopt a specific behavior or information (Filieri & McLeay, 2014; K. Zhao, Stylianou, & Zheng, 2018).

Though, previous research focus, in terms of health-related information exchange, were mostly on the social benefits (Wicks et al., 2012; Z. Yan et al., 2016), personal expectation and self-efficacy (Lin & Chang, 2018). The user's perception of the interactive features of social media with the presence of other users, the source of information, and review intensity have less attention in terms of attitude toward such online environment as a promoter of health awareness. Accordingly, the conceptual framework proposed in this research aims to examine how perceived interactivity of social media and source credibility effect users' attitudes toward using social media in promoting breast cancer awareness. It is also presumed that the reviews intensity moderates the relationship between users attitude and awareness of breast cancer via social media usage.

Literature Review

The research framework developed from several theoretical perspectives, which emphasizes a more holistic framework to predict the impact of social media usage on breast cancer awareness among women of generation Y in Malaysia.

Attitude towards Social Media Usage and Breast Cancer Awareness

Social media such as Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, and Instagram provide users with unique mechanisms to transmit and receive information and feedback in different forms of rating symbols, comments, and share. Prior research argued that users could be motivated for different reasons to engage in this online environment such as self-presentation (Joinson, 2008; Kietzmann, Hermkens, McCarthy, & Silvestre, 2011), social benefits (Kite, Foley, Grunseit, & Freeman, 2016; Moorhead et al., 2013), source credibility (Westerman, Spence, & Van Der Heide, 2014; Wu & Wang, 2011), and subjective norms (Chin, Lu, & Wu, 2015; S. Kim, Lee, & Yoon, 2015). Therefore, to enhance breast cancer awareness among women, it is essential to understand the most motivational factors that shape their attitudes toward utilizing social media in terms of health-related information exchange.

This research employs the Theory of Reason Action (TRA) and the Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM) to explore the motivational factors that will influence users attitude toward using social media, which in return

enhance breast cancer awareness. The TAR theory (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975), postulated that person's behavior is predicted by intentions, and their compliance to behave in a certain way is determined by their attitudes. In health context, prior research indicated that using social media results in valued health outcomes such as awareness (Hagg, Dahinten, & Currie, 2018; Lyson et al., 2018), and users attitudes toward utilizing these platforms improves their awareness of different health issues (Avcı, Çelikden, Eren, & Aydenizöz, 2015; Fuoco & Leveridge, 2015). For instance, users that holding believes that using social media with its interactivity features would improve the level of awareness about breast cancer due to their positive attitudes toward these online communication applications. Past research demonstrated that social media interactivity impacting attitude formation (Chung & Austria, 2010; Fortin & Dholakia, 2005), and therefore could be interesting and powerful outlets for continues usage and health-related information exchange (Chang, 2015; Lin & Chang, 2018).

The ELM which was developed by Petty and Cacioppo (1986) proposes that attitude formation and adoption of a specific behavior may be caused by two routes: the central route and the peripheral route. People often use source credibility as peripheral cues to process any information. The possible reason is that social media users receive a large amount of information from other users, which often causes information overload. When information overload occurs, users seek for a quick criterion to evaluate the usefulness of content (Forman, Ghose, & Wiesenfeld, 2008), sources authenticity, followers' number, or comments quantity (Watts & Zhang, 2008; W. Yan & Huang, 2014). Prior research found that author with good reputations will reduce users uncertainty about information quality (Liu, Liu, & Li, 2012; Shi, Hu, Lai, & Chen, 2018; W. Yan & Huang, 2014), which is resulted in more tendency of information adoption and exchange (Filiari, 2016; Filiari et al., 2018; Huang, Chen, Yen, & Tran, 2015). Consequently, users may consider source credibility as further useful indicators that enhance their attitudes toward social media usage for breast cancer awareness.

Likewise, people take another peripheral route that help in the process of decision making to adopt a specific information or behavior (Petty & Cacioppo, 1986), such as celebrity endorsements, or the information source attractiveness (Angst & Agarwal, 2009), information relevancy, value-added, accuracy, and quantity (Filiari & McLeay, 2014), likability, and ranking score (Filiari et al., 2018). Previous studies adopted several peripheral cues of online reviews that could vitally affect users attitude in the online context. This study uses this review intensity as a moderating variable, in which these peripheral indicators trigger a high level of engagement in breast cancer information exchange through social media. In summary, the conceptual framework of this study includes social media interactivity feature, source credibility and review intensity as predictors of users attitude toward using social media which might explain their engagement in this online environment as a tool for health information exchange. Hence, this study proposed:

H1: Women attitude toward social media usage positively affect breast cancer awareness.

Perceived Interactivity

Perceived interactivity holds several meanings or different standpoints which makes it difficult to defined (Lowry, Romano, Jenkins, & Guthrie, 2009). Previous research defined interactivity based on these different perspectives, such as features of technology, the process of message exchange, and users perception (Chang, 2015; McMillan & Hwang, 2002; L. Zhao & Lu, 2012). As this study attempts to measure the level of interactivity and to understand how users perceive their interaction experiences through social media, the user's perception is applied. Accordingly, perceived interactivity refers to the user's experiences as a simulation of interpersonal interaction and their sense that they are in the presence of other's social life (Thorson & Rodgers, 2006). Furthermore, users perception of interactivity emphasizes on different characteristics of interaction; person's interaction, social interaction and user's responsiveness to the content in any computer-mediated environment (Chang, 2015; Hoffman & Novak, 1996; L. Zhao & Lu, 2012). Past literature demonstrated that perceived interactivity is a multi-dimension construct (McMillan, 2002; L. Zhao & Lu, 2012). Thus, this study used three dimensions of human-to-human interactivity, human-to-message

interactivity, and human-to-community interactivity as these dimensions would capture the most notable interactivity features of social media.

The human-to-human interactivity reflects the provided platforms allow users to carry out interpersonal interaction with others. Prior research found that the easiness and overall control of interpersonal communication through social media enhance users' intention and continuance usage of these platforms (Chang, 2015; Lin & Chang, 2018; Shen, Cheung, Lee, & Chen, 2011). Meanwhile, the human-to-message interactivity reflects the responsiveness and user capability to process the content posted by users, which highlighted another aspect of social media interactivity. Dennis, Fuller, and Valacich (2008), and Lin and Chang (2018) stated that users ability to search, edit, and modify information in social media improves the quality and performance of communication, which is another detremenant factor of social media usage.

On the other hand, the human-to-community interactivity reflects users ability to interact with other peers or members in a virtual setting. Cheung and Lee (2010), and Seidman (2013) argued that the stable environment and the interactive nature of social media which fulfill their intrinsic need such as self-presentation and sense of belonging would directly affect users attitudes and intention to use these online platforms. Further, prior research indicated that the human-to-community interactive feature in social media is a significant determinant of user's satisfaction and continuance usage (Chang, 2015). Thus, the advanced interactivity feature of human-to-community will enhance users' attitude toward social media as an exchange tool of health-related information. The TAR theory (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975), suggested that person engagement in a specific behavior is predicted by their attitude and intention. Previous research indicates that users perception regarding technology interactivity features (J. Kim, Spielmann, & McMillan, 2012; Kirk, Chiagouris, Lala, & Thomas, 2015), such as active control, responsiveness, and the two-way interaction, significantly affects users attitude toward these technologies and intention to use. Based on the aforementioned, this study argues that users perceived interactivity dimensions have a significant and positive effect on users' attitude toward social media usage for breast cancer-related information. Therefore, the following hypotheses are proposed:

H2a: human-to-human interaction positively affects users attitude toward social media usage for breast cancer-related information.

H2b: human-to-message interaction positively affects users attitude toward social media usage for breast cancer-related information.

H2c: human-to-community interaction positively affects users attitude toward social media usage for breast cancer-related information.

SourceCredibility

Source credibility refers to judgments made by information recipient's concerning the trustworthiness and expertise of a communicator (Nan, 2013; Yoo & Gretzel, 2011). Various studies indicated that the effect of source credibility on users' attitude and behavior responses in the online context, proposing that highly credible sources yield a more positive attitude and higher compliance with specific behavior (Chu & Kamal, 2008; Spence, Lachlan, Westerman, & Spates, 2013). In another term, when users perceive a source to be credible, they are more likely to adopt message claims, resulting in more favorable attitudes and behavioral intentions to use social media for health-related information. Research shows that online health-related information has a substantial effect on the reader mind when it is generated by a knowledgeable and trustworthy person (Kareklas, Muehling, & Weber, 2015). Health information often is critical to health-related decisions (Owen, Fotheringham, & Marcus, 2002). Hu and Shyam Sundar (2010) stated that sources are powerful cues in affecting online user health information processing. (Petty & Cacioppo, 2012) Indicated that the sensitive nature of health information and in alignment with the model of ELM people are more likely to use a peripheral route when they are less-involved or capable of elaborating the message. Therefore, this study employs source credibility as a peripheral cue that influences users attitude toward social media usage for health-related information, in particular, the related breast cancer information. Previous researches have shown that information receivers are more likely to adopt (Chu & Kamal, 2008; Jin, Yan, Li, & Li, 2016), or disseminate (Liu et al., 2012; Shi et al., 2018) the information when it comes from expert, trustworthy and attractive source. Accordingly, this study argues that the credibility of the information

generator about breast cancer through social media exert a positive effect on the user's attitude towards these platforms for such purposes. Hence, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H3: Source credibility positively affects users attitude toward social media usage for breast cancer-related information.

The Moderating Effect of Review Intensity

Review intensity refers to the rating number, quantity, and the quality of the online review. Previous research illustrated significant effect of review intensity on several aspect, like attitude towards products (Lee, Park, & Han, 2008), purchase intention (Filieri et al., 2018; Park, Lee, & Han, 2007), and information adoption (Cheung, Lee, & Rabjohn, 2008; Filieri & McLeay, 2014). This indicates that users can use specific signals like review intensity to understand how other persons have evaluated a specific product or information in an online setting. The evaluation is a type of statics that provides the average ranking, and rating for posted information by online users (Filieri, 2015). However prior researches had put the focus to the impact of online reviews on shopping behavior (Floh, Koller, & Zauner, 2013), and user determinants to generate a review in an online environment (Majali, 2018). Review intensity could be external cues that enhance user's attitude towards using social media for health information exchange. On the contrary, ELM model posits that individuals who are lack less motivated and abled are more likely to use peripheral routes, which are mental shortcuts to evaluate the information quality and usefulness (Petty & Cacioppo, 1984). In this study, review intensity is employed as a moderating variable for users attitude toward using social media for breast cancer awareness. As review intensity increases, users have a positive attitude toward these platforms to improve their information about breast cancer. Conversely, when the overall ranking scores and relevancy are low, users are less motivated to adopt or engage in any social media activities (e.g., rating, share, and comment). Thus, this study proposes that:

H4: Review intensity moderates the relationship between users' attitude toward social media usage and breast cancer awareness.

Conceptual Framework

To understand the mechanisms of the underlying effect of social media usage on women of generation Y IN Malaysian, and to extend the prior theoretical contribution of social media influence on breast cancer awareness, a conceptual framework is developed. This framework examines the influence of perceived interactivity of social media and source credibility on a woman of generation Y attitudes to using these platforms as an information exchange tool about breast cancer, which will enhance their awareness of such potential risk. Furthermore, the model investigates the moderating effect of review intensity between women attitudes toward using social media and their level of awareness in this virtual community.

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework Model

Implication of the Study

Finding of this research is imperative for both research scholars and practitioners, especially in the Malaysian context. The results of this study enhance related parties to promote woman awareness about breast cancer through low-cost, convenience acceptable, and effective medium to reach the largest segment of the community. Using social media allows the practitioner to conduct health campaign without any barrier such as time or location. It can help the whole community to improve health behaviors as checking these social applications have become daily routine which in return will lead to higher health awareness and understanding of how to reduce health care expenditure. Also, this contributes to the body of knowledge by integrating the TAR and ELM which explain an individual's attitude and compliance to a particular behavior. The study includes the perceived interactivity of social media and source credibility as predictors of users' attitude toward using social media for breast cancer information. It is also proposed that review intensity moderates the relationship between users' attitude and awareness through social media usage. The finding will also provide a better understanding of the underlying motivations of social media usage for health-related information purposes, which in return improves women awareness about breast cancer.

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